

Home Quarantine as Home-Coming

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Home quarantine as a precaution to protect oneself from deadly pandemic covid-19 is indeed a unique opportunity for humans to home-coming. The metaphor 'Home-Coming' can be understood, both literally and symbolically. Home-coming literally means that we humans have gone too far in different crossroads in search of wealth that is transitory, social recognition that is fleeting, and the pleasures of the world that are momentary. Symbolically, home-coming could be understood as the need humans feel to return to their original home, their original self or return to the 'inner' self. The reason behind this is our obsession with 'activism,' always seeking ways and means solely in the direction of profit motive. But this overemphasis on outward actions can lead to adverse side-effects. What we need today is a good blend between these two extreme poles, one complementing the other. Most of the spiritual Gurus time and again have warned that authentic spirituality ought to deepen our journey in both directions. Henry Nouwen has rightly pointed out that: "Solitude is the furnace of transformation. Without solitude we remain victims of our society and continue to be entangled in the illusions of the false self." The sudden eruption of covid-19 sweeping the entire world, irrespective of all human made boundaries like developed or underdeveloped, rich or poor, without caste, creed and religion has taught us many hard lessons. No corner of the world is untouched and no life is unaffected by this pandemic.

The whole of humanity is facing unprecedented challenges. So, the question is: What lessons can we learn from 'Home Quarantine' during this time of covid -19? What are the opportunities we are exposed to?

From 'Hybridized Self' to 'Inner Self'

Home quarantine due to Covid-19 is a call to "authentic existence." Human existence is an on-going process. It is a journey that opens itself multi-directionally, a journey to oneself, to the other and to the Divine. As a result, humans are always on the process of refining themselves in a creative openness to oneself, to the other and the Divine. In other words, humans are called for a cosmic and borderless openness, seeing the whole cosmos as divinely saturated (Puthenpurackal). Authentic existence can be both a *call* and a *response*. It is a call to be finitely free and a response to be authentically oneself. But humans are lost in the world of "hybridization" (Puthenpurackal). Hybridization is understood not as the formation of hybrids by cross-breeding between different species. Metaphorically 'hybridization' refers to the insatiable craving humans have for *progress* in the exterior, leading to gradual *regress* in the interior. The rapid scientific and technological progress has led humans to greater heights but has failed to make them humane. Hybridization in this sense has shifted our focus from what is essential and original to what is outer and fleeting/transitory. As a result of hybridization humans think that their lives are *bettered* but they are in fact *altered*, distancing from the primordial. 'Hybridization' or progress in the exterior has created 'hybrid-humans,' pushing them further into their individual comfort zones, regressing in the 'inner' self, like the personal dimension, the social dimension, and the moral dimension.

It is a golden opportunity to return from one's masked hybrid self to one's primordial unmasked self, the home-coming to the 'inner' of the humans.

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In other words, we have given top priority to what philosopher Gabriel Marcel calls the '*having-dimension*,' rather than the '*being-dimension*' of humans. Home-Quarantine at this juncture due to the fast engulfing deadly disease Covid-19 can be such a golden opportunity to return from one's masked hybrid self to one's primordial unmasked self, the home-coming to the 'inner' of the humans.

Home Quarantine' is an opportunity and an invitation to delve deep into ourselves, be saturated by the Divine and reach out to others.

From 'Activism' to 'Silence and Solitude'

"All of humanity's problems stem from man's inability to sit quietly in a room alone," says French philosopher Blaise Pascal (2018, 139 "Diversion," 1670). Pascal clearly states that we humans are avoiding stillness and solitude. Without entertainment, distraction and diversion humans are forced to be alone with the inevitable 'truth' of existence, namely, that life is tough and humans are bound to be miserable or meant to suffer. It is so instinctive in us that we dread boredom and there is an urge to immerse our attention in external things than dwell on what is inside. In other words, what Pascal says is, we fear the 'silence of existence.'

What I believe is that the outbreak of the novel coronavirus disease Covid-19 and the home quarantine can be such a 'Pascalian Moment,' a great spiritual opportunity to sit quietly alone in our homes without distraction, and listen to the ego's incessant chirping about how restless and miserable this existence is. Could we say that the pandemic Covid-19 which has put the entire world in a complete lockdown is a call to cease senseless activity and a warning to spend more time as individuals going inward and grow in solidarity with the

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humanity? Could we say that Pascal is warning us against chasing after futuristic goals and our ceaseless craving to amass wealth, striving for power and prosperity that will not save us? Can we decide to put down our electronic devices, our brain numbing activities and be alone? All the cravings, the gadgets and the places we go to seek ‘divergence’ are completely locked down due to Covid -19. Amidst our fears of

this pandemic, we are called for a time of introspection, a time to rustle with the deepest questions of life and learn the art of silence and solitude. Pascal’s observation about our inability to sit quietly in a room by ourselves holds true: we are connected to everything else except ourselves.

From ‘Egoism’ to ‘Altruistic Actions’

Home-Quarantine also provides a golden platform for *altruistic actions*, which requires sacrifice on the part of the compassionate giver. It involves extending assistance to the other without expecting a benefit or a reward. It is to see the other as the legitimate goal in the giving. A well-known Biblical story is the Good Samaritan, the man from Samaria who generously gave his time and resource to the wounded victim. This story underscores the concept of sacrifice which lies at the heart of altruistic actions. Sacrifice is not only about material goods, but includes more elusive and highly valued social goods like interpersonal relationships, inclusion of those excluded of the society, help and listening ear to the migrant workers and the least of the society. Thus, ‘Home Quarantine’ is an opportunity and an invitation to delve deep into ourselves, be saturated by the Divine and reach out to others.

Reference

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